

HORIZON EUROPE PROJECT

Decentring the Study of Migrant Returns and Readmission Policies in Europe and Beyond (GAPs)

Decentring the Study of Migrant Returns and Return Policies

Politics and Realities of Return Migration in Four Transit Countries: Turkey, Morocco, Greece, and Poland

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Executive Summary

- This policy brief addresses increasing tensions and contradictions within return migration management in four strategically significant countries on the fringes of the European migration regime: Poland, Turkey, Morocco, and Greece. These countries are now focal areas of containment, being increasingly obliged to implement restrictive returns in compliance with EU externalization policies, securitization, and changing domestic pressures.
- Drawing on extensive qualitative data from the EU's Horizon Europe project GAPS, comprising life story interviews and ethnographic fieldwork, our analysis shows that return migration is rarely seen as a voluntary act. Migrants have to labor in a context dominated by legal insecurity, economic deprivation, and coercive control. They are constantly caught in a state of involuntary immobility in which they are barred from returning safely due to situations in their homelands, and, simultaneously, barred from moving on further due to restrictive asylum systems and enhanced border controls. While return policies are framed as humane and successful, they fail to reflect the lived reality of the very persons subject to them, who endure a state of insecurity, poverty.
- To address these challenges, this policy brief calls for a fundamental rethinking of return governance that is rights-based, realistic, and collectively owned by migrants and policy-makers. The structural causes of displacement should be prioritized in policy development, including serious consideration of the causative drivers of migration and human rights concerns. Return policies need to uphold the principle of voluntariness in practice by doing away with coercive pressures, increasing access to autonomous legal and psychosocial assistance, and allowing for informed choice-making, including through schemes such as exploratory return visits.
- Beyond this, successful return governance requires comprehensive assistance to migrants stuck in limbo, unable to return or regularize their status. Assistance should include access to legal avenues, reintegration assistance for returnees, and safe channels for onward travel if migrants choose this. Migrant agency—and the agency of diaspora communities in particular—and social networks should be recognized as integral

resources for facilitating effective and sustainable return processes. Proposed mechanisms such as return hubs should be considered in terms of the ethical and practical concerns they pose, including their potential to institute coercive frameworks and further increase precarity.

- Finally, a return policy that fails to acknowledge and remedy the overlapping legal, economic, and psychosocial constraints imposed upon migrants will remain ineffective, punitive, and ethically bankrupt. Only sustainable solutions that move beyond exclusionary enforcement rationalities and prioritize the dignity, rights, and the long-term flourishing of migrants themselves will work to fix the return policy “gaps”.

What GAPS did and what evidence underpins this brief

This analysis draws on a multi-sited qualitative research design conducted across Turkey, Morocco, Greece, and Poland. Combining anthropological and sociological fieldwork methods, the study integrates in-depth life stories and semi-structured interviews to capture migrants’ aspirations, social ties, and mobility choices. A multilevel analytical framework—spanning individual experiences, meso-level network influences, and macro-level policy environments—enabled a comprehensive understanding of return dynamics. Data were transcribed and coded iteratively using both deductive and inductive strategies to uncover patterns across diverse contexts.

Evidence and Analysis: what needs to change

Return Migration Governance: Trends and Challenges

Return policies in each of these countries have become increasingly restrictive, with a shrinking space for legal residence and a growing number of oppressive return

measures. Domestic politics and economic uncertainty have encouraged governments to prioritize security and exclusionary tactics over humanitarianism. An emphasis on return governance in fact conceals underlying structural issues, including the lack of safe and legal mobility channels and inadequate support mechanisms for integration.

While returns are typically framed as “voluntary,” they tend to be motivated by compounded economic, legal, and social pressures that reduce any meaningful difference between coercion and choice. One strategy that states use is to run both voluntary and forced return programmes at the same time. Turkey, for example, has a differentiated return policy—encouraging return for Syrians through “voluntary” programs and regularly deporting Afghans. Morocco balances assisted voluntary return (AVRR) operations with forced returns. Greece utilizes forced returns, AVRR, and has a rising rate of border pushbacks—particularly since 2020. Poland concurrently imposes brutal pushbacks at its Belarusian border while giving protection to Ukrainian refugees, which illustrates very varying treatment by nationality. Thus, migrants are offered different options according to their nationality with the result is that they are embedded in systems of return with high degrees of coercion.

Social and Economic Pressures on Migrants

Across all four countries, migrants face acute economic destitution, too often complemented by situations of informal employment. Precarious labor is common, particularly in the manufacturing sector, such as textiles, but also in farming, restaurants, and housekeeping. Work life is characterized by poverty-level wages, abuse, and a lack of legal protection. In Turkey, the ongoing economic crisis and police harassment exacerbate migrant vulnerability, while in Morocco and Greece, mass

employment in informality is coupled with meager access to services and soaring costs of living. Migrants from Poland, particularly from the Global South, face situations where employers are not aware of procedures for formal residency and work permits, economic pressures and limited state support.

Legal precariousness also contributes to these challenges. Complex and discretionary residence procedures, prolonged status renewal delays, and exploitative intermediaries render migrants perpetually "deportable." States take advantage of this with: Turkey exercising discretionary detentions and deportations; Greece conducting police sweeps and other mass deportation operations; Poland deploying night raids; and Morocco resorting to forced relocations and police harassment. These measures erode migrants' sense of stability and safety and contribute to trauma, fear, and limited access to work or social services.

Agency and Strategic Decision-Making Amid Constraints

Despite these strict controls, migrants show creativity and agency. They strategically decide to remain, return, or move further based on their economic capital, legal prospects, and social networks. Options are restricted, however. Triandafyllidou (2018) reminds us that forced migration always entails aspects of choice and constraint, and our interviews demonstrate that migrants employ subtle tactics—such as invisibility, secondary movements, or utilization of diaspora networks—to circumvent mobility restrictions.

Migrant mobility - from the very first decision to leave an origin country - is shaped by both insecurity and market realities. The differentiation between "refugee" and "economic migrant" is eroded as both are subject to violence and poverty after migrating (Crawley et al. 2018). Accounts from migrants

in GAPs research support this point. Afghans in Turkey cite Taliban control, ethnic/religious oppression (especially of Hazaras and women), and economic disintegration as the reason for migrating; Syrians identify civil war, ISIS, and worsened services. Palestinians, Sudanese, and Ethiopians speak of ongoing conflict and poverty. Economic necessity and social provision are overarching motivators for migrants in Morocco. Those in Greece report having fled political oppression, instability, and poverty, whereas those in Poland fled war, persecution, and domestic violence.

Perceptions of Return and Onward Movement

Return is rarely an option. Security issues—of being conscripted, persecuted, or murdered—remain paramount. Material hardship in home countries (no jobs, food shortages, lack of infrastructure) and the psychological tolls of failure (e.g., having to sell assets to emigrate) are powerful deterrents. It is only in certain limited situations—political stability, economic betterment, family ties, or elderly care—that return becomes desirable. Diaspora groups and transnational networks play a significant role in return trajectories, either by providing information or necessary support and mutual encouragement.

For a majority of migrants, return is seen as evidence of failure and even shameful, making hopes of forward mobility overwhelmingly positive. Migrants aspire to make it to Germany or Sweden, attracted by the more regular asylum processes, chances for citizenship, schooling, and networks already established there. These ambitions are frequently hindered by legal restrictions, costs, and dangers involved with irregular travel. Most migrants thus stay in Turkey, Morocco, Greece, or Poland, surviving in uncertain legal conditions and waiting—often indefinitely—for their circumstances to change.

Entrapment in Restrictive Systems

Turkey, Morocco, Greece, and Poland's return migration policies are shaped by global agreements (primarily with the EU), local security concerns, and political-economic pressures. They all have particular characteristics—differential treatment of migrants in Turkey, violent pushbacks in Greece, dual-track return mechanisms in Morocco, and discriminatory border patrols in Poland. Yet, despite these differences, we observe a common outcome: migrants are caught between coercive return processes and

the non-existence of safe onward mobility. They find themselves in a state of "involuntary immobility," unable to return due to insecurity and poverty in their homelands, and unable to move onward due to exclusionary border regimes and constrictive asylum policies. Successful return policies must deal with the root causes of displacement, offer real legal alternatives, and create circumstances in which return can be truly voluntary. Otherwise, return policies will remain inhumane.

Policy Recommendations

An effective EU return policy must balance the need for "efficient" returns with the fundamental rights and individual circumstances of migrants. To succeed in the long term, it should foster genuine cooperation with third countries and help address the root causes of migration.

1. Establish conditions of true voluntariness for returns: Return should be a genuine, informed, and uncoerced decision—not one made under duress or in the absence of meaningful alternatives. Although the European Union's newly proposed regulation introduces some positive steps, such as the creation of return and reintegration counselling services, further measures are needed to ensure that the principle of voluntariness is fully respected in practice. True voluntariness requires that individuals are fully informed of their rights and options, have adequate time to consider their decisions, and receive access to independent legal advice and psychosocial support. It also necessitates the absence of indirect forms of pressure, such as the threat of detention, withdrawal of services, or the imposition of deadlines that imply punitive consequences. One promising approach to support informed decision-making is the provision of exploratory return visits. These are temporary returns to the

country of origin that allow individuals to assess conditions without losing their legal status or rights in the host country. Such initiatives, piloted in Turkey in 2025 for Syrians considering return, enable migrants to make more confident and informed choices about whether to return permanently, particularly when facing uncertainty about safety, reunification with family members, or access to livelihoods.

2. Policy frameworks that blur the distinction between voluntary and forced return are problematic. For example, a dual-track model that promotes voluntary return while simultaneously threatening removal for non-compliance can undermine the credibility and ethical standing of voluntary return schemes. To address this, policies must draw a clear line between voluntary return procedures and enforcement measures. Return decisions should not be driven by the prospect of punitive action, nor should migrants be coerced into compliance through the manipulation of incentives or time pressure. Institutional mechanisms must be in place for individuals to voice concerns, receive fair consideration, and challenge decisions through transparent and accessible procedures. Ultimately, reinforcing migrant agency and procedural justice should be at the heart of any return strategy. Only then can return policies

achieve both legitimacy and long-term effectiveness.

3. Provide counseling, support and information: The proposal's inclusion of return counselling and support can be seen as an attempt to balance enforcement with assistance and to potentially mitigate the GAPS finding that return can be seen by many migrants as evidence of failure and even shameful. Information about return and reintegration options needs to be comprehensive and easily accessible, tailored to individual circumstances and in languages migrants understand.

4. Address the predicament of migrants who are trapped between return and onward movement: Many migrants in the EU remain in prolonged limbo: unable to return safely because of insecurity at home, yet unable to move forward or regularise their status. The EU's drive for mutual recognition of return decisions to reduce secondary movements risks reinforcing this, especially where protection and support are weak. While mutual recognition can improve enforcement and coordination, it must not mean automatic returns without individual assessment or consideration of alternatives. In order to be effective and equitable, return policies need to be based on a more integrated understanding of migrants' im/mobility pathways, shaped by risk, constraint, and hope. This recognizes the complexity and requires shifting away from deterrence-oriented policies. The EU must offer pan-European, sectoral assistance to those at risk of return, such as vocational training, legal pathways, and basic services. Such an initiative would allow migrants to pursue sustainable options—either through safe return, regularization, or onward movement in the EU—while respecting their rights and potential for the future. Above all, mutual recognition should not come at the cost of procedural justice or protection obligations. Compliance with the principle of non-refoulement and individualized examination is paramount. An effective EU

return policy needs enforcement to be accompanied by assistance and solidarity and address the structural conditions producing and perpetuating migrant precarity.

5. Recognizing and Utilizing Migrant Networks and Diaspora Organizations: Diaspora groups and transnational networks play a significant role in return trajectories. We recommend actively engaging with these networks to provide information, facilitate voluntary return, and support reintegration in the country of origin. This approach would recognize migrants as active participants in the return process and leverage their existing social capital.

6. Rethinking the Use of Return Hubs in Light of Ethical and Practical Concerns: The European Commission's proposal to establish return hubs raises serious questions regarding both the viability and also the ethical implications of such mechanisms. Central to these concerns is the recognition that return to the country of origin is rarely the preferred option for many migrants. As shown in the GAPS study, migrants often aspire to onward migration in search of better legal protection, economic opportunities, and an escape from discrimination. Placing individuals in return hubs in third countries does not necessarily alter these aspirations; many may continue to seek onward movement, which could undermine the stated objectives of such hubs.

7. Moreover, many migrants face persistent, well-founded fears of persecution, violence, and economic deprivation in their home countries. These structural barriers—repeatedly described by migrants themselves—make return from a hub in a third country no more acceptable than return from the host state. If return hubs are meant as an intermediate step toward repatriation, such unresolved risks are likely to reduce individuals' willingness to engage in voluntary return from these locations.

8. Concerns also arise regarding the coercive nature of returns, even when labeled as “voluntary.” Political, economic, and social pressures often leave migrants with little real choice, and there is a serious risk that transfer to return hubs could be perceived—and experienced—as another layer of coercion. While the proposed exclusion of families with minors and unaccompanied children acknowledges the vulnerability of certain groups, GAPS research makes clear that many other migrants facing return decisions also endure significant vulnerabilities that may be exacerbated by transfer to a hub.
9. The establishment of return hubs also threatens to deepen migrants’ sense of insecurity. In the GAPS study, many participants described living with a constant fear of detention and deportation. The possibility of being relocated to a return hub in a third country, especially where legal protections and safeguards are unclear or perceived as inadequate, would likely heighten this insecurity. For many, it could amount to yet another episode of displacement—disrupting already fragile lives, separating families, and reinforcing a cycle of uprooting and instability.
10. Finally, return hubs risk replicating the failures associated with the “hotspot” model, including prolonged legal limbo, procedural delays, and widespread legal uncertainty. Unless such hubs are grounded in a clear rights-based framework and ensure genuine consent and procedural fairness, they are unlikely to provide durable solutions and may instead perpetuate or intensify migrant precarity.
11. **Before considering the possibility of return for those who**

wish to, the root causes that led to migration from the origin country in the first place need to be recognized:

The EU Commission's proposal for a new Common European System for Returns focuses mainly on procedures for returning third-country nationals without a right to stay in the EU. It situates return within a broader framework of “balanced and comprehensive partnerships” with third countries where migration framed as a core issue (p. 4). The proposal also highlights that, by increasing the effectiveness of the EU's return system, the EU can make better use of improved readmission cooperation and a wide range of external tools, including visa policy, trade, development and diplomacy (p. 4). While these broader instruments may indirectly contribute to tackling some structural drivers of migration by fostering stability and opportunities in third countries, the core emphasis of the regulation remains on return procedures. Unless such underlying causes are explicitly addressed, return cannot be considered genuinely voluntary or sustainable for those who choose it.

Concluding note

The GAPS evidence shows that the EU’s challenge is not to increase returns, but to dismantle the conditions that make return coercive and unsustainable: legal precarity, economic exclusion, psychosocial harm, and blocked mobility pathways in contexts such as Turkey, Morocco, Greece, and Poland. Effective return must be rights-based, transparent, mobility-aware, and support durable futures beyond enforcement alone.

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Project identity

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Further reading	For more detailed analysis, please consult the GAPs project’s website – “Publications”: https://www.returnmigration.eu/publications-gaps See Annex for “Debunking Return Migration Policy Myths with the GAPs research”.

Project summary

GAPs is a Horizon Europe research project that aims to conduct a comprehensive multidisciplinary study of the drivers of return policies and the barriers to and enablers of international cooperation on return migration. The overall aim of the project is to examine the disconnects and discrepancies between expectations of return policies and their actual outcomes by decentering the dominant, one-sided understanding of “return policymaking.” To this end, GAPs:

- examines the shortcomings of the EU’s return governance;
- analyses enablers of and barriers to international cooperation, and
- explores the perspectives of migrants themselves to understand their knowledge, aspirations and experiences with return policies.

GAPs combines its approach with three innovative concepts:

- A focus on return migration infrastructures, which allows the project to analyse governance gaps;
- An analysis of return migration diplomacy to understand how relations between EU member states and third countries hinder cooperation on return and
- A trajectory approach which uses a socio-spatial and temporal lens to understand migrant agency.

GAPs is a three-year interdisciplinary research project (2023–2026) coordinated by Uppsala University and the Bonn International Centre for Conflict Studies (BICC) with 17 partners in 14 countries on four continents. GAPs’ fieldwork and desk research are conducted in several countries, including Afghanistan, Canada, Germany, Greece, Iraq, Jordan, the Netherlands, Nigeria, Morocco, Poland, Sweden, Tunisia, Türkiye, and the UK.

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